

POLITICAL SCIENCES

CRITICAL ANALYSIS OF THE METHODS USED TO COMBAT CORRUPTION IN MEXICO: DURING THE AMLO ADMINISTRATION

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Abstract

Corruption has been considered one of the biggest problems facing governments worldwide, and Mexico has been no exception. This paper explores the issue of corruption from the perspective of anti-corruption models during the presidency of Andrés Manuel López Obrador (AMLO). One of AMLO's main talking points was the need to combat corruption peacefully, using the phrase "hugs, not bullets." He created two programs aimed at reducing the problem. This paper descriptively examines and critically reviews Mexico's position on the international stage, concluding that the programs failed to impact Transparency International's ranking. Therefore, it concludes that anti-corruption policies must be accompanied by other mechanisms for clearly positioning the State to achieve effective results.

Keywords: Corruption, public policy, AMLO, Mexico

I. Introduction

Corruption is not a problem unique to Mexico, but impunity is. Here, scandals do not have effective consequences in the courts (Sánchez, 2017, 15). As long as impunity is the rule, rather than the exception, it will not be possible to break with the tradition that most harms our public life and our prosperity (Pardinas, 2015, p. 15). In Mexico, the issue of corruption involves three things. First, the perception of corruption, particularly in the public sector, grows year after year. Second, in measurements of the problems plaguing our country, corruption has positioned itself as one of the main problems, even above poverty. Third, the impunity surrounding corruption has remained constant. As with other crimes, misdemeanors, and infractions in Mexico, those defined as acts of corruption are almost never punished, at least 95% of the time (Casar, 2015, p. 5). What characterizes a country with institutions resistant to the onslaught of corruption is its capacity to prevent, prosecute, and punish it. Mexico's problem, in addition to corruption itself, is the exceptional impunity that accompanies it (Grandet, 2015, p. 99). In this regard, it is worth noting that institutional efforts to combat corruption in Mexico have been lukewarm and largely ineffective (Kaiser, 2014, pp. 49-50). In 1982, during the administration of Miguel de la Madrid, the Secretariat of the Comptroller General of the Federation (SECOGEF) was established. In 1994, under the administration of Ernesto Zedillo, it adopted the name Secretariat of the Comptroller and Administrative Development (SECODAM), and in 2003, during the administration of Vicente Fox, it became the Secretariat of Public Administration (SFP). In all three cases, these were agencies dependent on the head of the Executive Branch, lacking autonomy and technical or political independence. Progress has also been made in the formation of external or inter-organic control bodies such as the Superior Audit Office of the Federation

(ASF) of the Chamber of Deputies of the Congress of the Union (1999), the Federal Institute for Access to Information (now INAI) in 2002 and the Special Prosecutor's Office for Combating Corruption in the Federal Public Service of the Attorney General's Office of the Republic. On the legislative front, two relevant laws were introduced: the Federal Law on the Responsibilities of Public Servants of 2002 and the Federal Law on Anti-Corruption in Public Procurement of 2012. Finally, the National Anti-Corruption Commission (CNC), proposed by Enrique Peña Nieto in 2012 to replace the Ministry of Public Administration (SFP) as an autonomous control body, was not accepted by the political parties. Therefore, after a long process of deliberations and consensus-building, they approved the National Anti-Corruption System (SNA) and its implementing laws in 2015. In this chapter, our central argument is framed by three related assumptions: 1) that there are two models for combating corruption in Mexico, one built by the SNA, and the other, the anti-corruption strategy of the government of Andrés Manuel López Obrador; 2) that these are two anti-corruption models that do not have coordination policies and concurrent areas between them; and 3) that the operation of the two separate anti-corruption models cannot effectively combat the complex problem of corruption in Mexico.

II. The fight against corruption within the National Anti-Corruption System (SNA)

The importance of the anti-corruption agenda at a global level, the adoption of this agenda by some legislators, the greater access to public information, the growing corruption scandals in the country and the organized work of numerous civil society organizations increased the political pressure for which the National Anti-Corruption System (SNA) was approved by both chambers on April 21, 2015 (Casar, 2015, p. 52), during the last stretch of the government of Enrique Peña

Nieto. The National Anti-Corruption System (SNA) involves constitutional modifications in several sections, including the legislative powers of Congress; the strengthening of the Superior Audit Office of the Federation (ASF); the internal control bodies of the branches of government and constitutionally autonomous bodies; the creation of the Federal Court of Administrative Justice (from the current Federal Court of Fiscal and Administrative Justice); the system of responsibilities, which includes not only public servants but also private individuals; the ratification of the head of the Ministry of Public Administration (SFP); the extension of the statute of limitations for serious administrative offenses; as well as the transitional provisions of the reform (Senate of the Republic, 2015, p. 7).

The National Anti-Corruption System (SNA) is comprised of four pillars: the Ministry of Public Administration (SFP); the Superior Audit Office of the Federation (ASF); the Specialized Prosecutor's Office for Combating Corruption (FECC); and the Federal Court of Administrative Justice (TFJA). A key element uniting these four pillars is the creation of a Coordinating Committee composed of the heads of the four anti-corruption institutions, as well as the head of the National Institute for Access to Information (INAI), a representative from the Federal Judiciary Council, and a representative from the Citizen Participation Committee. Its powers will consist of designing and promoting public policies to audit and control public resources and to prevent, control, and deter administrative offenses and acts of corruption (Casar, 2015).

At the federal level, the National Anti-Corruption System (SNA) is 95% complete after its approval by both houses of Congress in 2015. The situation in Mexico City is baffling, as it has not appointed its Selection Committee (a position also lacking at the federal level), Citizen Participation Committee, Coordinating Committee, or Technical Secretariat (a situation also present in Morelos). Secondly, three entities (Baja California Sur, Baja California, and Mexico City) had not yet filled the position of Anti-Corruption Prosecutor. This suggests that, more than six years after the SNA's creation, it remains incomplete. Thirdly, Mexico City's lack of commitment to combating corruption is striking, as it has not filled all five SNA positions: Selection Committee, Citizen Participation Committee, Coordinating Committee, Technical Secretariat, and Anti-Corruption Prosecutor.

Fourth, regarding the operation of anti-corruption prosecutors, the National Anti-Corruption System (SNA) itself points out that, despite progress, the systems still face challenges. For example, anti-corruption

prosecutors have drastically reduced budgets and lack the technical and administrative autonomy to establish their own budgetary priorities, sign collaboration agreements, and appoint their own public prosecutors and police officers. Anti-corruption prosecutors enjoy full constitutional autonomy in only three states, while in the rest they must answer to the state attorney general's office and depend on it for funding. In thirteen states, the current anti-corruption prosecutor was nominated directly by the governor or the attorney general, rather than through a democratic process involving input from the state legislature or an open call for applications. This lack of autonomy, in addition to making anti-corruption prosecutors more susceptible to political influence on sensitive investigations, is one of the reasons why their role is limited and, with limited resources, the anti-corruption prosecutor's hands are tied in the fight against corruption in the states.

Mijangos Borja is the official representing the Attorney General's Office (FGR) on the National Anti-Corruption System (SNA) Coordinating Committee and has the constitutional mandate to investigate corruption cases. The office she heads, the Specialized Prosecutor's Office for Combating Corruption, should have the capacity to take on key cases like these and strengthen its work. One issue that the government of Andrés Manuel López Obrador has failed to resolve is its constitutional responsibility to appoint the 18 anti-corruption magistrates who should serve on the Federal Court of Administrative Justice (TFJA). The absence of these magistrates is delaying the prosecution of dozens of serious administrative offenses and the full integration of the National Anti-Corruption System (SNA). As of 2021, the SNA is not yet fully operational, and the TFJA is a key component in prosecuting serious crimes related to the fight against corruption.

National Anti-Corruption Policy (PNA)

The Citizen Participation Committee (CPC) within the framework of the National Anti-Corruption System (SNA) has been fundamental in including the voices of the population in anti-corruption policy. This group of five civil society leaders focused largely on designing a National Anti-Corruption Policy (PNA) that outlines 40 key priorities for combating corruption in Mexico (PNA, 2021, p. 1). In its assessment of the National Anti-Corruption Policy (PNA), the CPC establishes that the central problem is the inability to control corruption, making it necessary to prevent, detect, and effectively punish it. This assessment of corruption involves four priority areas and strategies, as shown in Table 1.

Table No. 1

National Anti-Corruption Policy (NAP)

Axes	Strategies
1) Corruption and impunity	Prevention, detection, reporting, investigation, prosecution, and sanctioning of administrative offenses. Prosecution and administration of justice in matters of corruption-related crimes.
2) Arbitrariness and abuse of power	Professionalism and integrity in public service Institutional processes Auditing and oversight
3) Improved management and points of contact between government and society	Government-citizen contact points: procedures, services, and public programs Government-private sector contact points
4) Social involvement in the control of corruption	Citizen participation: monitoring, collaboration, and co-creation. Shared responsibility and corporate integrity. Education and communication for combating corruption.

Fuente: (PNA, 2021, pp. 1-2).

For Mariclaire Acosta, former President of the CPC, what she calls "the most significant and noteworthy achievement of the CPC" during her tenure was the development of the National Anti-Corruption Policy (PNA). This policy was developed through a series of public consultations held throughout the country to

gather input from civil society organizations, academics, the business community, public officials, and other non-governmental actors. The PNA establishes forty priorities for combating corruption in Mexico (see Figure 1).

Once the National Anti-Corruption Plan (PNA) establishes its forty strategies as part of its fight against corruption, it is determined that there are risk conditions in said fight, among which the following stand out:

1) Public service at the national level is not structured on minimum bases of merit, professionalism, integrity and consistency (but rather a system of plunder prevails);

2) The planning, budgeting and expenditure processes of public institutions lack transparency and minimum criteria to justify decisions;

3) Administrative failures and crimes involving acts of corruption are not investigated and punished effectively, so reporting is not an effective tool for controlling corruption;

4) Internal control bodies, as well as those responsible for administering and prosecuting justice, lack sufficient capacity and resources;

5) Areas of opacity and arbitrariness persist in the interaction between citizens and companies with the government, when carrying out procedures or requesting services;

6) Public procurement processes occur in an environment of opacity, discretion, and lack of clarity regarding their effects on effective delivery

In summary, the National Anti-Corruption Plan (PNA) is one of the most important tools for combating corruption within the National Anti-Corruption System (SNA), as it was the product of deliberation and participation by various governmental and non-governmental actors. It needs wider dissemination to become better known both within the anti-corruption system itself and among civil society. The PNA is a relevant instrument in the fight against corruption from the citizen's perspective, so it would be advisable to promote its dissemination and discussion among broad segments of society.

National Digital Platform

During the forum "National Digital Platform: Sub-national Interconnection and 2020 Progress," the Executive Secretariat of the National Anti-Corruption System (SESNA) presented the progress at the state level, as well as the new functionalities and tools for connecting to the National Digital Platform (PDN) by obligated entities. SESNA has launched a beta version of the National Digital Platform, which, once completed, will house all declarations submitted by public servants. The platform will also make publicly available information related to officials who have been investigated or sanctioned for a criminal or administrative offense (SNA, 2021, pp. 1-2).

During the event, participants emphasized the need for all federal entities to accelerate their connection to the National Digital Platform (PDN) by May 2021 at the latest. They highlighted the cases of Jalisco and Aguascalientes as examples, which achieved this despite the adverse conditions caused by the COVID-19 pandemic.

It was reported that this new version of the National Public Registry (PDN) already has four of its six systems functional. This means that the interoperability model has been tested and that it already contains real data in the following systems: Asset and Conflict of In-

terest Declarations (System 1); Public Servants Involved in Procurement Procedures (System 2); Sanctioned Public Servants and Private Individuals (System 3); and Public Information on Procurement (System 6).

The head of the National Anti-Corruption Secretariat (SESNA) highlighted that the Ministry of Public Administration (SFP), the State of Mexico, and the governments of Aguascalientes and Jalisco are the first obligated entities to connect to System 1 of the Platform, and they are doing so eight months ahead of the legal deadline. "This is undoubtedly another achievement for the Platform and for the fight against corruption." He announced that SESNA is working on the development of the "Digital Anti-Corruption Marketplace," which will be a space with a series of tools ready for any obligated entity to download and use. It will also serve as a platform for those who have developed tools they wish to share, making them available to everyone (SNA, 2021, p. 3).

In summary, they emphasized the importance of the National Anti-Corruption Platform (PDN) as a tool of the Mexican State, essential for addressing the problem of corruption, and to which all public institutions at the federal, state, and municipal levels are obligated to contribute the information in their possession. The PDN is a platform within the National Anti-Corruption System (SNA) that allows for greater data integration in the fight against corruption.

Investment in the fight against corruption

Although Andrés Manuel López Obrador had stated during his presidential campaign that combating corruption was one of his priorities, these intentions are not reflected in the content of the 2019 Federal Expenditure Budget (PEF), which shows a 12% drop in the budget allocated to the main institutions and units responsible for fighting corruption, such as: the National Institute for Transparency, Access to Information and Protection of Personal Data (INAI); the Superior Audit Office of the Federation (ASF); and the Ministry of Public Administration (SFP), among others.

The following graph, which uses 2015 as a base year, shows the largest increase in the budget for combating corruption in the 2018 Federal Expenditure Budget (PEF), with an 11% rise. This increase was intended to consolidate institutions and strengthen cooperation among the components of the National Anti-Corruption System (SNA), but this funding was not continued in 2019.

Source: 2019 Annual Report, IMCO.

The anti-corruption policy of Andrés Manuel López Obrador's government is contradictory, as it is based on austerity measures and budget cuts that have undermined the continuity of activities of key institutions in the fight against corruption, instead of investing in solving the problem.

The National Anti-Corruption System (SNA) is a medium- to long-term project. If the secondary legislation is approved within the timeframe established by the decree amending the Constitution regarding the fight against corruption, this legislation will take an additional two years at the federal level alone. The System itself is not yet fully operational throughout the country. "As such, the National Anti-Corruption System is a roadmap, not a new institution" (SNA, 2021, p. 2). In 2021, the integration process of the Federal Court of Administrative Justice (TFJA) was still incomplete, and some entities, such as Mexico City, had not yet appointed any of their anti-corruption bodies or members.

In short, combating corruption requires not only political will but also sufficient funding, the autonomy and independence of anti-corruption prosecutors, and the professionalization of public servants to ensure that the efforts of civil society within the framework of the National Anti-Corruption System (SNA) are respected. The SNA must once again be considered the platform that builds institutional bridges between the government and citizens to combat corruption in Mexico, a situation that is not occurring under this administration of the Fourth Transformation.

III. The fight against corruption with AMLO

As previously mentioned, the government of Andrés Manuel López Obrador prioritized combating corruption during its electoral campaign. However, its actions and anti-corruption strategy do not consider the National Anti-Corruption System (SNA) relevant. Within its own anti-corruption strategy, it has utilized five federal government agencies and entities, including: (1) the Ministry of Public Administration (SFP);

(2) the Financial Intelligence Unit (UIF); (3) the Attorney General's Office (FGR); (4) the Tax Administration Service (SAT); and (5) the Mexican military (Ministry of National Defense and Ministry of the Navy).

The role of the SFP in combating corruption

First, the Ministry of Public Administration (SFP) is the body responsible for internal control and combating corruption in Mexico. Its anti-corruption efforts include two key initiatives: 1) the National Program to Combat Corruption and Impunity and Improve Public Management 2019-2024 (PNCCIMGP); and 2) the Internal and External Whistleblower Platform. As will be described, both of these tools differ in form and substance from the National Anti-Corruption System (SNA) strategy, and they do not establish points of contact or coordination for anti-corruption efforts.

National Program to Combat Corruption and Impunity, and to Improve Public Management 2019-2024

The National Program to Combat Corruption and Impunity, and to Improve Public Management 2019-2024 (PNCCIMGP), which is under the responsibility of the SFP and was developed under its responsibility, has the following as its priority objectives in this area: Combatir frontalmente las causas y efectos de la corrupción;

1. Combat levels of administrative impunity in the Federal Government;
2. Promote the efficiency and effectiveness of public administration;
3. Promote the professionalization and efficient management of human resources in the Federal Public Administration; and
4. Promote the efficient and responsible use of Mexican state assets.

Of these five priority objectives for combating corruption, the PNCCIMGP establishes their relevance in the current context of the government of Andrés Manuel López Obrador, in the following terms:

Table No. 2.

Relevance of the objectives	
Objetives	Relevance
1) To combat head-on the causes and effects of corruption	To understand the magnitude of this scourge, it suffices to point out that, as a percentage of GDP, corruption amounts to 9%, according to calculations by the World Bank and the Bank of Mexico. Furthermore, our country ranked 138th out of 180 countries according to Transparency International's 2018 Corruption Perceptions Index, receiving a score of 28.0 that year. According to INEGI (the Mexican National Institute of Statistics and Geography), based on public perception, corruption ranks second among the country's main problems for 6 out of 10 people, second only to insecurity and crime; moreover, 86% of the population believes that the federal government operates within corrupt environments.
2) Combat levels of administrative impunity in the Federal Government	It is a priority for the Federal Government to take effective action to curb corruption and impunity, guaranteeing citizens an efficient and constantly evolving Federal Public Administration. Through the proposed priority strategies, it is possible to implement a special program that optimizes the use of the necessary tools for the Federal Government to directly combat potential acts of corruption and consolidate a system that effectively enforces administrative sanctions and reduces impunity.
3) Promote the efficiency and effectiveness of public management	It is geared towards coordinating actions related to promoting austerity in public spending, as well as efficiency and effectiveness in public management. These aspects are relevant within the framework of the National Development Plan's objectives, as they seek to oversee the development of each government action undertaken to ensure compliance with the principles of economy, efficiency, transparency, and integrity, and that the resulting savings are used to generate well-being.
4) Promote the professionalization and efficient management of human resources in the APF	It is important to develop a strategy to disseminate, impact, and strengthen the tools available to public servants, with the intention of rethinking integrity in public service, through awareness-raising actions that will materialize through dissemination and specialized training on issues of ethics and public integrity, in order to provide knowledge and reinforce the skills that public service personnel have.
5) Promote the efficient and responsible use of Mexican State assets	The relevance stems from the need to have sufficient planning tools to analyze real estate assets in a comprehensive manner, and thus be able to identify the spaces whose best use will serve as a trigger not only for public real estate activity, but also for the regional projects of this administration and the economic development of the country.

Source: (SFP, 2020).

Based on the establishment of strategic objectives, the PNCCIMGP comprises a set of priority strategies and specific actions, which are carried out by agencies and entities of the Federal Public Administration. It is

important to note that these strategies are disconnected and lack points of contact and coordination with the National Anti-Corruption System (SNA), as can be seen in diagram #2.

PRIORITY STRATEGIES AND SPECIFIC ACTIONS

SOURCE: SFP (2020).

Source: SFP (2020).

According to the SFP, the timely implementation of the National Program Against Corruption and Impunity (PNCCIMGP) will contribute, through combating corruption and impunity and improving public administration, to achieving the most important objective of the Fourth Transformation government: that by 2024 the population of Mexico will be living in an environment of well-being (SFP, 2020). However, the National Anti-Corruption Program (PNA) has forty priority actions that are more feasible to implement, while this federal program is more descriptive, with complex goals that are difficult to quantify.

Platform of Internal and External Whistleblowers of Corruption

The SFP recently launched a new platform called "Internal and External Whistleblowers Against Corruption," where citizens can report public officials for acts of corruption, sexual harassment or assault, as well as human rights violations. This government platform has four objectives, which are as follows:

- 1) To facilitate the reporting of bribery, embezzlement, and misuse of public funds by citizens and public servants without fear of reprisal;
- 2) To guarantee the confidentiality of communications;
- 3) To protect anonymity when requested by the whistleblower;
- 4) To serve as a tool in the fight against corruption and impunity.

This is a platform that the SFP (Ministry of Public Administration) makes available to citizens to report serious acts of corruption involving federal public servants. The platform can report: 1) bribery; 2) embezzlement; and 3) misuse of public funds.

The platform offers two options for anonymously reporting an alert: 1) basic: using your browser, but

without providing identification or contact information; and 2) advanced: fully guaranteeing anonymity in the digital environment using an anonymization network. The most commonly used tool is the TOR network (SFP, 2021).

In comparison to the National Anti-Corruption Platform (PDN), which has broader scope in its modules for combating corruption within the National Anti-Corruption System (SNA), such as asset and conflict of interest declarations; public servants involved in procurement; and public servants and private individuals sanctioned for public procurement, the "Internal and External Whistleblowers of Corruption" platform designed by the Ministry of Public Administration (SFP) only aims to combat three forms of corruption (bribery, embezzlement, and misuse of public funds) without broader anti-corruption objectives. Another approach would be for both platforms to be linked and complemented to expand the reach of the fight against corruption.

Financial Intelligence Unit (UIF)

The second instrument of the López Obrador administration's anti-corruption strategy is the Financial Intelligence Unit (UIF). The UIF's main tasks consist of implementing and monitoring mechanisms for preventing and detecting acts, omissions, or transactions that could favor, aid, abet, or cooperate in any way with the commission of the crimes stipulated in the Federal Penal Code.

The Financial Intelligence Unit (UIF), as a branch of the Ministry of Finance and Public Credit, is the central national body responsible for:

- Receiving reports of financial transactions and notifications from those engaged in vulnerable activities;

- Analyzing financial and economic transactions and other related information;
- Disseminating intelligence reports and other documents useful for detecting transactions likely linked to money laundering (ML) or terrorist financing (TF), and, where appropriate, filing the corresponding complaints with the competent authority.

In particular, within its purview, the UIF carries out various activities as part of the fight against corruption, both domestically and internationally. Among these actions are:

- Mexico developing measures to combat corruption and advance the implementation of the OECD Anti-Bribery Convention;
- Mexico assuming the Vice Presidency of the Group of Experts for the Control of Money Laundering (GEVALEX);
- Mexico holding the Co-Presidency of the Joint Americas Group of the FATF International Cooperation Review Group

The Financial Intelligence Unit (UIF) has been one of the most important instruments in the fight against corruption during the Fourth Transformation. Its tracking of funds belonging to individuals suspected of public and private corruption has led to the freezing of bank accounts and the prosecution of various public figures in Mexico. For the first time, the UIF is being used effectively to combat corruption in the performance of its duties.

The effort to investigate significant corruption cases in the current López Obrador administration, such

as the Lozoya and Robles cases and those of other officials involved in these scandals, was not solely the work of the Attorney General's Office (FGR). The charges filed are largely the result of investigations carried out by the Financial Intelligence Unit (UIF) within the Ministry of Finance and Public Credit (SHCP). This office is responsible for combating money laundering and other financial crimes.

However, while the UIF has collaborated extensively with the SNA in this effort, it is not currently an official member of the system. Recently, the government of Andrés Manuel López Obrador and MORENA senators have proposed amending the Constitution to grant the UIF a permanent seat on the SNA's Coordinating Committee. The UIF's anti-corruption efforts should be highlighted in this anti-corruption strategy because they have secured the evidence necessary for investigations and for judges to issue arrest warrants in each of these relevant cases, which represent a comprehensive fight against corruption.

IV. Two different ways of fighting corruption in Mexico: the National Anti-Corruption System (SNA) and AMLO's strategy

The two previous sections briefly described the two models for combating corruption in Mexico: the National Anti-Corruption System (SNA) and AMLO's anti-corruption strategy. At least five instruments can be identified in which both anti-corruption strategies have marked differences and priorities in their implementation, as shown in Table 3:

Table No. 3

Comparative analysis of the two anti-corruption systems

Tools	SNA	SFP
Participants	Coordinating Committee of the National Anti-Corruption System Citizen Participation Committee National Oversight System State and Local Anti-Corruption Systems Anti-Corruption Prosecutor's Office Federal Court of Administrative Justice	Ministry of Public Administration Attorney General's Office Financial Intelligence Unit (UIF) Tax Administration Service (SAT) Armed Forces (Army and Navy)
Strategy	National Anti-Corruption Policy (PNA)	National Program to Combat Corruption and Impunity, and to Improve Public Management 2019-2024
Platforms	National Digital Platform	Internal and External Whistleblowers of Corruption
Budgetary allocations	Decreased resources ²	Increased resources
Priority	Low priority for the AMLO government	A high priority for the AMLO government.

Source: own elaboration.

In the first two years of López Obrador's administration, several high-ranking officials from the administrations of Felipe Calderón Hinojosa and Enrique Peña Nieto, as well as former governors, have been accused of alleged corruption. Some of them are currently facing criminal proceedings in Mexico, while others have been implicated in the United States (Molina, 2020, p. 1).

The main difference between this administration and previous ones is its declared commitment to fighting corruption. The president has shifted the focus of the so-called fight against corruption to the Attorney General's Office, the Tax Administration Service (SAT), and the Financial Intelligence Unit (UIF), and there is a public perception that the government is

² The 2020 budget proposal includes a 57% increase in funds designated for the SFP, while funds for other aspects of the System will have substantial reductions (for example, the budget of the Specialized Prosecutor's Office for Combating Corruption is reduced by 70%).

working on this task. However, corruption in procedures and services, which includes federal and state governments, continues to grow. And unfortunately, large-scale transnational corruption remains unpunished in Mexico. Regarding the most high-profile cases, there are still no convictions, and no misappropriated assets have been recovered. There are changes, yes, but they are not yet being reflected in the public consciousness (Molina, 2020, p. 3).

According to Eduardo Bohórquez, director of Transparencia Mexicana, the López Obrador administration has neglected the National Anti-Corruption System (SNA), both in terms of the necessary budgetary support for its operation and its implementation at all three levels of government. Instead, efforts to combat corruption have focused on the Attorney General's Office (FGR), the Tax Administration Service (SAT), and the Financial Intelligence Unit (UIF), in addition to the significant role of the armed forces in the construction of various public works projects.

In the comparative analysis of the anti-corruption models—the National Anti-Corruption System (SNA) and the AMLO administration—there are two entities that are part of both strategies, albeit with different roles. In AMLO's strategy, the Ministry of Public Administration (SFP) is responsible for internal control and combating corruption and impunity within the executive branch, while in the SNA, it is a relevant body but also forms part of the system's other elements. With its National Program to Combat Corruption and Impunity and Improve Public Management 2019-2024 and its "Internal and External Whistleblowers" platform, its institutional strategy is endogenous and operates within the administrative structure of the federal public administration. In contrast, the SNA has a different roadmap with its National Anti-Corruption Policy (PNA) and the National Digital Platform (PDN), following guidelines across different levels of government—federal, state, and local—and incorporating greater citizen participation alongside other social and non-governmental actors in the fight against corruption.

Regarding the Attorney General's Office (FGR) in both anti-corruption models, its role is crucial as an autonomous body that allows for more effective prosecution and combats corruption at all levels of government (Sánchez, 2017, p. 510). The difference lies in the fact that the government of Andrés Manuel López Obrador has insisted on intervening in matters of personal and political interest, thus calling into question its supposed autonomy.

For Bohórquez, the biggest shortcoming is not in the tools or the regulatory frameworks, but in the results. Corruption networks have not yet been dismantled, the cases of former governors remain pending

trial, and there has been no asset recovery or reparations for victims. There are more tools, more powers, more work, but the results are still very similar to those of the past.

For his part, Marco Fernández, coordinator of the anti-corruption program at México Evalúa, described the current administration's fight against corruption as merely rhetorical, ineffective, and selective. He commented that there is no systematic investigation and prevention strategy to combat the problem. On the contrary, the current administration cites, for example, the case of Manuel Bartlett, head of the Federal Electricity Commission (CFE), who was not only exonerated, but no investigation was even conducted to explain the proliferation of real estate holdings, which are inconsistent with his record as a public official.

Another contradiction of President López Obrador is that during his campaign he assured that direct awards of contracts would not be abused during his term, yet this has become a pattern in his administration. He also mentioned that cabinet members have exploited loopholes in the law to avoid declaring all of their assets.

In short, in 2021 Mexico had two anti-corruption strategies: the National Anti-Corruption System (SNA), the product of a long process of political and parliamentary deliberation, and Andrés Manuel López Obrador's own strategy, which, through his own federal government agencies and entities, has launched a campaign to combat corruption. These anti-corruption strategies are disconnected, lacking points of coordination that would allow for a comprehensive fight against corruption involving various agencies, levels of government, and a participatory citizen strategy. Perhaps at some point, the two strategies could be integrated into the complex task of effectively and decisively curbing and containing corruption, with results that are perceptible to all citizens.

International Perception of Corruption

The problem of corruption, as we have been explaining, is not exclusive to any one country. According to Transparency International, "There is no country in the world that is free from corruption" (2025). Despite the serious problems that corruption brings, primarily affecting the most vulnerable groups in different countries, including children who suffer from health problems, malnutrition, low academic performance or lack of access to education, and the worst cases of child exploitation in its various forms, Mexico is no exception. In fact, according to this international agency, the situation in Mexico has become increasingly chaotic, as shown in Table 1 below.

Table #1.

Time series of Mexico's ranking in the International Corruption Index.

Año	Score	Ranking
2025	27	141
2024	26	140
2023	31	126
2022	31	126
2021	31	124
2020	31	124
2019	29	130
2018	28	138
2017	29	135
2016	30	123
2015	31	111

Source: Prepared by the author using data from Transparency International <https://www.transparency.org/en/cpi>

According to Transparency International's methodology, the rating scale ranges from 1 to 100, with 100 being the highest. The ranking is assigned based on the score obtained, and 180 countries are evaluated. Although several countries may occupy the same position, this is because the ranking is based on the points obtained, not on a single, fixed position. For this reason, Mexico's ranking is not particularly low, but its score is extremely poor. As can be seen, Mexico's points have been decreasing from 2015 to 2025, causing it to fall behind other countries in the ranking. Therefore, it can be inferred that the policies implemented in Mexico's anti-corruption models have not had a positive outcome; on the contrary, they have served to further fuel the increase in corruption in the country.

Conclusions

As mentioned, no country in the world is exempt from corruption. However, the added problem is that instead of improving its ranking as a sign of progress in combating corruption, the country in question falls further and further down the international rankings, as is the case with Mexico. This clearly indicates that anti-corruption programs have not been sufficient to mitigate the problem that plagues the administrative system and is reflected in public policies through the impressions of the beneficiaries and users of these programs. Therefore, it is concluded that: 1) there are two models for combating corruption in Mexico: the National Anti-Corruption System (SNA) and the anti-corruption strategy of the government of Andrés Manuel López Obrador; 2) there are few links and coordination policies between these two anti-corruption models; and 3) operating anti-corruption models in isolation cannot effectively combat corruption in Mexico.

While President Andrés Manuel López Obrador's anti-corruption strategy, two years into his administration, has not seen significant progress in combating corruption, specialists agree that although cases have received more media attention, there have been no results in terms of convictions or recovery of assets. This represents a major outstanding issue for the country, for democracy, and above all, for the citizens.

In the case of the National Anti-Corruption System (SNA), which is in the process of being fully integrated, with over ninety percent of its bodies and appointments completed at all three levels of government, a permanent budget is needed to cover the operation

and functioning of its structures, full autonomy for anti-corruption prosecutors in the states, and greater professionalization of the personnel involved in combating corruption so that they can achieve better results. It is also concluded that the fight against corruption must be accompanied by clear and decisive actions that establish a clear position for the State and that are reflected in tangible results so that the social benefits can be measured later.

On the other hand, expectations remain the same: that in the future there will be better actions aimed at mitigating or reducing the problem of corruption in Mexico. It is possible that in the next six-year term, through electoral competition, better options can be generated and translated into action.

References:

1. BROOKS, Darío. "México: el inédito rol del ejército y la marina en el gobierno de AMLO (más allá de la seguridad pública)", en *BBC News Mundo*, 1 diciembre 2020. Disponible en <https://www.bbc.com/mundo/noticias-54850024>
2. CASAR, María Amparo. *México: anatomía de la corrupción*. CIDE, IMCO. México, 2015.
3. GRANDET, Carlos y JAURY, María José. "Leciones internacionales del combate a la corrupción", en *La corrupción en México: transamos y no avanzamos*. IMCO. México, 2015.
4. IMCO, INFORME ANUAL 2019, ([HTTPS://IMCO.ORG.MX/WP-CONTENT/UPLOADS/2020/03/INFORME-ANUAL-2019.PDF](https://imco.org.mx/wp-content/uploads/2020/03/INFORME-ANUAL-2019.PDF)).
5. Ver en <https://sna.org.mx/2020/09/23/presenta-sesna-avances-y-nuevas-funcionalidades-para-conectarse-a-la-plataforma-digital-nacional/>. Consultado el 10 de marzo de 2021.
6. KAISER, Max. *El combate a la corrupción, la gran tarea pendiente en México*. Miguel Ángel Porrúa. México, 2014.
7. MOLINA, Héctor (2020). "Dos años de gobierno de AMLO: cómo va el combate a la corrupción", en *El Economista*, 25 de noviembre de 2020. Disponible en <https://www.economista.com.mx/politica/Dos-anos-de-gobierno-como-van-las-acusaciones-20201125-0152.html>. Consultado el 10 de marzo de 2021.

8. PARDINAS, Juan E. "Impunidad, corrupción y competitividad", en *La corrupción en México: transamos y no avanzamos*. México, IMCO, 2015.

9. Plan Nacional Anticorrupción, 2021. Disponible en <https://sna.org.mx/>. Consultado el 10 de marzo de 2021.

10. SÁNCHEZ GONZÁLEZ, José Juan. *La corrupción en la administración pública y el Sistema Nacional Anticorrupción*. IAPQROO, Cámara de Diputados, Fundación Universitaria de Derecho, Administración y Política S.C. FUNDAp. Querétaro, México, 2017.

11. SAT, 2021. Disponible en https://es.wikipedia.org/wiki/Servicio_de_Administración_Tributaria

12. Senado de la República, 2015. *Dictamen de las Comisiones Unidas de Puntos Constitucionales; de Anticorrupción y Participación Ciudadana; de Gobernación, y de Estudios Legislativos. Segunda, sobre la minuta de proyecto de decreto por el que se reforman, adicionan y derogan diversas disposiciones de la Constitución Política de los Estados Unidos Mexicanos, en materia de combate a la corrupción*. 16 de abril de 2015.

13. SFP. *Programa Nacional de Combate a la Corrupción y a la Impunidad, y de Mejora de la Gestión Pública 2019-2024*. SFP. México, 2020. Disponible en <https://funcionpublica.gob.mx>. Consultado el 10 de marzo de 2021.

14. SFP, 2021. Disponible en <https://alertadores.funcionpublica.gob.mx/>. Consultado el 10 de marzo de 2021.

15. SNA, 2021. Disponible en <https://sna.org.mx/>. Consultado el 10 de marzo de 2021.

16. Transparencia Internacional. (2025). Índice de Percepción de la Corrupción 2025. Recuperado de <https://www.transparency.org/en/cpi/2025> Consultado 10 de Enero 2026.

17. UCol, 2021. *Ahorra México más de 1 bdp por combate a la corrupción: AMLO*. Disponible en <https://elcomentario.ucol.mx/ahorra-mexico-mas-de-1-bdp-por-combate-a-la-corrupcion-amlo/>. Consultado el 10 de marzo de 2021.